

Deliverable D7.1

Plan for dissemination and exploitation including communication activities

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v2.0	02.10.2025	Dorothea Dörr (Euro-Biolmaging ERIC), Beatriz Serrano-Solano (EMBL-Bio-Hub)	Final draft approved

Acronyms and Abbreviations

AI	Artificial Intelligence
BMZ	BioImage Model Zoo
CoFest	Collaboration, Cooperation, and Contribution Festivals
D	Deliverable
EOSC	European Open Science Cloud
ERIC	European Research Infrastructure Consortium
HRB	Horizon Results Booster
KER	Key Exploitable Result
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
ML	Machine Learning
PU	Public
RI	Research Infrastructure
v	Version
WP	Work Package

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Executive Summary

AI4Life is a project from the Horizon Europe Work Programme that brings together 10 institutions from 8 countries into a 3-year effort supported by a 4 million EUR budget. The project aims to bring state-of-the-art AI-based image analysis to life scientists while bridging the gap between computational experts and researchers. AI4Life supports this goal by developing, deploying, and sharing AI models, FAIR datasets, and training resources.

This deliverable outlines the overall dissemination and exploitation strategy of AI4Life. As part of this effort, Work Package 7 (WP7) previously delivered a detailed report ([Deliverable D7.2](#), Month 30) covering the project's communication efforts, as well as the organisation and outcomes of workshops, hackathons (CoFests), and other interactive events.

To guide this dissemination and exploitation plan, WP7 conducted a stakeholder analysis to identify target audiences that AI4Life addresses: life scientists, image analysts, computational experts, AI4Life partners, AI4Life consortium bodies, industry, national and international organisations, policymakers, funding agencies, and the general public.

AI4Life implemented a coherent visual identity and branding strategy, complemented by templates, videos, and outreach materials to ensure consistent messaging. Dissemination channels include a project website, newsletters, social media, publications, workshops, CoFests, and open calls designed to maximise visibility and adoption.

Exploitation activities have focused on ensuring the long-term use and impact of AI4Life results. Key outcomes include Open Calls, Challenges, the BioImage Model Zoo, BioEngine, the AI4Life Chatbot, community engagement programs, FAIR datasets, and metadata standards. These have been consolidated into nine Key Exploitable Results (KERs) with high scientific and technological potential. Follow-up activities, including integration into European research infrastructures (e.g., Euro-BioImaging) and collaborations with affiliated projects such as AI4EOSC and RI-SCALE, ensure that AI4Life resources are maintained, reused, and expanded.

Finally, the sustainability strategy builds on three complementary pillars: community co-development, integration into European infrastructure, and governance continuity. A participatory governance framework coordinates ongoing development, contribution, and maintenance of AI4Life resources, securing the project's long-term impact within the bioimaging community.

1. Introduction

The AI4Life project is part of the European Union's Horizon Europe Research and Innovation Programme, led by the project coordinator Euro-BioImaging and participated by 10 partners, 4 of them being European Research Infrastructures themselves. The project started in September 2022 and ended in August 2025.

AI4Life aims to bring state-of-the-art AI-based image analysis to life scientists by establishing and supporting innovative services targeting researchers in the life sciences and computational methods developers in AI and computer vision.

More specifically, the objectives of AI4Life are

- **Objective 1: Democratised availability of AI-based image analysis methods** as a FAIR service accessible through the AI4Life service landscape and computationally powered by the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC) infrastructure.
- **Objective 2: Establish standards** for the submission, storage, and FAIR access of reference data, reference annotations (ground-truth), trained AI models, and trainable AI methods.
- **Objective 3: Simple model deployment, sharing, and dissemination** of AI-based methods as a new developer-facing service of the [BioImage Model Zoo \(BMZ\)](#).
- **Objective 4: Organise Open Calls and Challenges** for outstanding image analysis.
- **Objective 5: Empower common image analysis platforms with AI tools.**
- **Objective 6: Organise outreach and training events.**

This deliverable is part of WP7, *Communication, Outreach, and Training*. WP7 contributes to Objectives 3, 4, and 6 by raising awareness of AI4Life and the opportunities it offers to life scientists. WP7 develops and implements a communication and outreach strategy and training activities designed to engage a wide range of audiences who could benefit from using AI-based analysis tools on image data.

This document outlines the plan for disseminating and exploiting AI4Life outcomes, highlighting the actions and strategies adopted to maximise visibility, uptake, and long-term impact.

2. Description of work

2.1. Stakeholders

The main stakeholders of AI4Life fall within the following categories:

Stakeholder category	Definition
Life scientists	Scientists from the public and private sectors use imaging techniques and are interested in exploring AI methods for their research.
Microscopists	Staff who work at imaging facilities support researchers in acquiring data.
Image analysts	Staff, often working at imaging facilities, who support researchers in their image data analysis.
Research Software Engineers	Experts working on using and developing computational methods, e.g., using AI to help analyse image data.
PI / Facility Heads	Senior scientists responsible for research groups or facilities.
AI4Life partners	Participants of the project who either provide services and infrastructure or are potential users.
AI4Life Consortium Bodies	<p>There are 4 Consortium Bodies in AI4Life:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Project Management Executive Board</i>: comprises the Administrative Coordinator, the Scientific Coordinators, and the Project Manager, and is in charge of the project management. • <i>Steering Committee</i>: supervisory body for executing the project that reports to and is accountable to the General Assembly. The Steering Committee consists of the Work Package Leaders and the Project Manager. • <i>Executive Board</i>: oversees the Virtual Access ("VA") infrastructures and regularly assesses all services provided. The General Assembly appoints the Executive Board, and the Scientific Coordinators steer it. • <i>Open Calls Selection Committee</i>: oversees the Challenges and Open Call review and selection processes.

Industry	Members of the industry interested in using the AI models provided at the BMZ and participating in the opportunities that AI4Life offers in the form of Open Calls and Challenges.
National and international organisations and initiatives	National, European, or international initiatives, projects, and organisations in the imaging or AI fields.
Policymakers and funding organisations	Entities that support the implementation of science and the integration of science into policies.
General public	Individuals outside the primary users interested in the project outcomes, such as imaging and/or AI enthusiasts, member states, scientific journals, and media (print, online, TV, radio, and journals).

AI4Life offers different services to stakeholders, summarised in a [section on the website](#) and the table below.

Stakeholders	Open Calls	Workshops	Consume FAIR AI models	Consume / Deposit Data	Challenges	Hackathons	Contribute FAIR AI models	Relevant AI tech updates	AI & Data Handling Helpdesk	Stay informed
Life Scientists										
Microscopists										
Bioimage Analysts										
Research Software Engineers (RSEs)										
PI / Facility Heads										
Industry partners										

2.2. Branding

AI4Life presents a coherent branding strategy and provides the consortium members with assets to facilitate their use for internal and external purposes.

2.2.1. Logo

The AI4Life logo features the giraffe, with a link to the [BioImage Model Zoo](#) branding. Since the project's launch, the giraffe has become a popular and identifiable stakeholder icon. It symbolises the role of the project as a service to the scientific community: AI4Life helps you to analyse your image data better, so you can not only pluck the low-hanging fruit.

The logo is available for white and dark backgrounds in 3 file formats (PNG, PDF, ai).

2.2.2. Representative image

Besides the logo, AI4Life provides an extra image representing the project's aim: bridging the gap between the life scientists' expertise and the availability of methods and expertise contributed by computational experts. As a symbol of AI4Life, the giraffe supports life scientists on their way to computational methods.

All images are available in two formats: JPG and PDF.

2.2.3. Templates

Templates are available to all project partners, ensuring clear and coherent communication of messages for different purposes:

- Presentations: a slide deck with an overview of the project (goal, partners, objectives, structure) is available in pptx format. All partners contribute to a more technical slide deck addressing specific audiences throughout the project.
- A one-slide summary of the project is ready to be inserted into presentations.
- Letterhead document for official communications.
- Template for deliverables of the project.
- Poster with general information about the project, its scope, and activities.
- Abstract describing the project.
- Regularly updated AI4Life impact factsheet.

2.2.4. Videos

The consortium planned several videos for outreach and training purposes. To facilitate the creation and coherently present them, we have created [intro and outro videos](#) for the partners to use at the beginning and end of their video recordings, tutorials, screencasts, or other video material.

2.2.5. Guidelines

All the mentioned assets (logo, representative image, videos, and templates) are part of an [Outreach Support Pack](#), publicly available on the project's *Google Drive*. The goal is to facilitate and encourage the use of communication materials. All of them align with the branding guidelines:

STYLETILE

Heading:
Kumbh Sans Regular

Sub Heading:
Kumbh Sans Bold

Body Text: Kumbh Sans Light
 Lorem ipsum dolor sit amet. Ullaborum et velectis alicid molorem porpore ribusci lluptati consernatqui que voluptatiam et fuga (link). Itatecum eni re, nobit excepe pe natis modion nimus, optatur magnates. Alitis dolupta culles di reriaturi aut laciet plique voluptas alia dis earum untorror sequam, volupta quossi quiat aut etur, ventionsequo to que que volesed ut elesci volenda deb-itaq uisquae catorum ipiet, et labo. Cuptatur, sinihil eos debis et dolo berum que nus minctestrum la que voluptatur aut qunt.

www.ai4life.eurobioimaging.eu

font <https://fonts.google.com/specimen/Kumbh+Sans>

graphical elements

logo on white logo on dark

USE WHEN LOGO HAS MORE SPACE

USE WHEN LOGO NEEDS MORE VISIBILITY

primary colors

#214858	#046374	#007d7e	#009475	#48ab5d	#91bb3b
R47 G72 B88	R4 G99 B116	R0 G125 B126	R0 G148 B117	R72 G171 B93	R145 G187 B59
C83 M58 Y44 K39	C87 M41 Y39 K25	C84 M28 Y47 K13	C82 M16 Y64 K2	C71 M3 Y79 K0	C51 M4 Y92 K0

secondary colors

#fde724	#f5547	#95b0b4	#f8fff8
R253 G231 B36	R255 G85 B71	R149 G176 B180	R248 G255 B248
C4 M3 Y88 K0	C0 M78 Y66 K0	C47 M21 Y27 K3	C4 M0 Y5 K0

gradient

AI4Life follows the spelling convention for the project's name by only capitalising the first two letters ('AI') as shown in the project's logo.

2.2.6. Giveaways

Giveaways (postcards, stickers, pins, mugs, t-shirts, bags, camera covers, and glass cleaners) have been distributed at the events organised by AI4Life and stakeholders, being mindful of the environmental impact that they could create.

2.3. Text

AI4Life offers boilerplate text and key messaging that project partners can reuse in different contexts and dissemination channels to support consistent and effective communication.

2.3.1. Boilerplate text

A boilerplate text is available in the section *About us* on the website:

<https://ai4life.eurobioimaging.eu/about-us/>

AI4Life in a nutshell

AI4Life is a Horizon Europe-funded project that combines the computational and life science communities.

Its goal is to empower life science researchers to harness the full potential of Artificial Intelligence (AI) and Machine Learning (ML) methods for bioimage analysis, particularly microscopy image analysis, by providing services and developing standards aimed at both developers and users.

AI4Life promises to create harmonised and interoperable AI tools & methods via open calls and public challenges and bring these developments to researchers via strategic outreach and advanced training.

The services provided and solutions developed within the AI4Life framework are crucial to solving today's microscopy image analysis problems and will contribute to boosting the pace of biological and medical insights and discovery in the coming years.

The [BioImage Model Zoo](#) and FAIR data principles are core facets of the AI4Life project.

2.3.2. Key messages

Objectives

- Empower life science researchers to use AI and ML methods for image data analysis.
- Establish standards for FAIR AI models and data that enable interoperability between resources.
- Provide infrastructure to deploy and share models.

Motivation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Bridge the gap between state-of-the-art AI methods and life science problems.
Approach	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Organise Open Calls to support life scientists in solving their problems. • Organise Challenges for computational experts to solve complex AI problems. • Train life scientists to use AI models. • Engage computational experts through hackathons and CoFests to improve and develop new models.
Outcomes	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Make models available at the BioImage Model Zoo. • Make training data available at the BioImage Archive. • Establish standards that allow interoperability between resources.

2.4. Dissemination

Dissemination occurs through different channels, with the website being the first contact point for partners and external members.

2.4.1. Website

The website (<https://ai4life.eurobioimaging.eu/>) is the primary source of information for all the stakeholders in the project. Euro-BioImaging has full editorial control over the content and encourages and welcomes contributions from all partners by sharing them with the WP7 leader. The website is structured as follows:

Main page	Subpage	Content	Status
About us	Objectives	Objectives of the project	Online
	Partners	Partners involved in the project: communities and RIs	Online
	Structure	Work Packages and distribution of work	Online
	Outcomes	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Timeline with Deliverables and Milestones - Publications acknowledging the project 	Online
	Contact	Ways to interact and engage with the project	Online

Services		Links to services offered by the project: – Biolmage Model Zoo (Biolmage.IO) – Biolmage Archive (BIA) – BioEngine – Biolmage.IO Chatbot – Containers	Online
Open Calls	About the Open Calls	Information about the past, current, and upcoming Open Calls	Online
	Use Cases	Examples of user projects gathered from the Open Calls	Online
Challenges		Information about the three challenges organised throughout the project	Online
Engage		How to engage with AI4Life for different stakeholders	Online
Events		List of workshops and hackathons with significant contributions by AI4Life partners	Online
News		Examples of news pieces published on the website: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • New model in BMZ • New community partner in BMZ • New publication from the partners • New service available • New standard developed • Deliverable published • Open Call announcements: launch, deadlines, updates... • Challenge announcements: launch, deadlines, updates... • Event organised • Interviews 	Online
Help		Direct user support	Online

2.4.2. Social media

AI4Life has accounts on different social media platforms:

Platform	Account
LinkedIn	https://www.linkedin.com/company/ai4life-eu-project
Mastodon	https://qoto.org/@AI4Life
Twitter	https://twitter.com/AI4LifeTeam
Bluesky	https://bsky.app/profile/ai4life.bsky.social
YouTube	https://www.youtube.com/@ai4life

The primary goal of the *Mastodon*, *Twitter*, and *LinkedIn* accounts is to promote activities, share relevant content about the project, and retweet/repost from the AI4Life partners. Given the current changes in the social media landscape, AI4Life now has an account in Bluesky, too. *YouTube* hosts original content developed in the project for training and outreach purposes.

2.4.3. Newsletter

We release quarterly email newsletters in March, June, September, and December to address everybody interested in the project news and outcomes. All the [published newsletters are also accessible on the AI4Life website](#), including *ad hoc* communications upon relevant events within the project, such as the Open Calls: <https://ai4life.eurobioimaging.eu/?na=view&id=9>.

Anyone can subscribe via the online form at <https://bit.ly/ai4life-newsletter>. The subscription process is double opt-in registration and ensures compliance with GDPR by requesting the subscriber's name, affiliation, and email address. Additionally, the signup form is also available on our website.

Euro-Biolmaging creates and sends the newsletter using WordPress. The content is related to AI4Life and the consortium member activities, with third-party announcements, only included when considered relevant to the recipients.

Euro-Biolmaging regularly requests content from the project partners to be included, first, in the *News* section of the website, and second, gathered in the quarterly newsletter:

Since the AI4Life stakeholders are diverse and from a mix of life sciences and computational backgrounds, the language must be understandable for both.

2.4.4. Publications

Publications are a key aspect of scientific research. We encourage the Open Call applicants and participants in Open Challenges to publish their results in open-access journals.

In hackathons (CoFests), we recommend participants write the outcomes in preprints and upload them to [BiohackXiv](https://www.biorxiv.org/) and/or the AI4Life website.

To acknowledge the funding, publications need to use the following sentence:

AI4Life has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under grant agreement number 101057970.

To keep track of the publications acknowledging AI4Life, Euro-Biolmaging maintains a [Zotero Group Library](#) with integration with WordPress that displays the content in the [Outcomes section of the website](#).

2.4.5. Zenodo

For deliverables, reports, and other outcomes of the project, the [Zenodo AI4Life Community](#) is used instead.

2.4.6. Other channels

The imaging community gathers around the [Image.sc](#) forum, where questions and answers are exchanged vividly. AI4Life plans to use this forum extensively to stay in touch with the community and to provide support regarding AI4Life-related topics. For that purpose, a profile for the project has been created: <https://forum.image.sc/u/ai4life>.

WP7 requested all AI4Life partners to provide communication contact details (name, description, type of channel, contact point, and who can reach out) so that the stakeholders can disseminate outcomes and results further. At the time of writing this deliverable, we have collected 56 channels of different sorts:

Channels collected by the AI4Life partners for dissemination

2.5. Impact measurement

2.5.1. Tracking and monitoring

All WPs are responsible for the dissemination and exploitation of the project outcomes.

To monitor the impact, we have set up a *Dissemination Registry* and circulated it among the partners to include all the events and project outcomes. This registry contains the date, event type, event name, host institution, organisers, audience, speaker, and contribution title.

2.5.2. Communication metrics

We gathered and analysed metrics from the social media platforms (Twitter, LinkedIn, YouTube) and the AI4Life website. WordPress makes available all the information related to the spread of the newsletter, such as the subscriber trend, clicks, and opening rates.

Additionally, an impact factsheet has been created to gather some of the project's Key Performance Indicators (KPIs). The factsheet and other communication metrics build a subset of the project's KPIs that have been defined to monitor and evaluate its pathway towards its objectives systematically.

2.6. Exploitation

This section outlines AI4Life's efforts and strategies to identify relevant project results and outputs, efficiently exploit them, and thus ensure maximum project impact during and beyond AI4Life's funded project time.

2.6.1. AI4Life results and outputs

Project results and outputs were regularly identified and characterised by all project partners through project-internal and periodic reporting processes at months 12, 20, 28, and 36. Results were characterised based on the Horizon Europe reporting format and monitored and approved through the AI4Life Steering Committee. In the following sections, we provide an overview of different result groups.

2.6.1.1. Project deliverables and publications

All AI4Life deliverables and additional project documentation are openly available on the [project's Zenodo community](#) webpage. In October 2025, the community provided access to 39 resources, including mainly reports but also datasets, software, presentations, and posters. In addition, more than 40 AI4Life-related scientific articles and technical reports were openly published throughout the project's lifetime, promoting Open Science and broad community engagement. Other selected project information and news can be found through the [AI4Life project website](#), which will be maintained according to Horizon Europe guidelines following the project's official end.

2.6.1.2. Open Calls

Open Calls are a way for AI4Life to offer computational support, direct help, and solutions to life scientists. AI4Life launched three Open Calls in total (2023 Q1, 2024 Q1, and 2024 Q4), each aiming at supporting life scientists and microscopists to analyse their image data. A timeline for Open Call launches has been published on the [AI4Life website](#).

To maximise visibility, promotional materials, including dedicated posters, Zoom backgrounds, pre-prepared texts, and summary slides, were distributed among all partners, encouraging dissemination with their networks and communities. The central contact point for applicants was the mailing list ai4life@eurobioimaging.eu.

Following the first Open Call, we refined our selection process by introducing a consultation phase. This phase was designed to clarify the scope and suitability of top-ranked projects and to offer constructive and timely feedback to promising proposals.

Selected projects received deep learning support from AI4Life experts; several have already led to scientific publications. Additionally, we are preparing a “best practices and take-home messages” manuscript, reflecting lessons learned from the broad range of applications received and the selection process.

A growing collection of supported use cases has also been made public on our [website](#) and [AI4Life GitHub](#).

OPEN CALL for Bioimage Analysis Support

- I need help analysing image data
- I need help creating training data
- I need help applying Deep Learning to my research data

Apply by **March 31**

ai4life@eurobioimaging.eu

OPEN CALL for Bioimage Analysis Support

8 projects awarded

- Analysis of the fiber profile of skeletal muscle.
- Atlas of Symbiotic partnerships in plankton revealed by 3D electron microscopy.
- Automated and integrated cilia profiling.
- Identifying senescent cells through fluorescent microscopy.
- Image-guided gating strategy for image-enabled cell sorting of phytoplankton.
- Leaf tracker plant species proof.
- SGEF, a RhoG-specific GEF, regulates lumen formation and collective cell migration in 3D epithelial cysts.
- Treat CKD.

ai4life@eurobioimaging.eu

OPEN CALL for Bioimage Analysis Support

Apply by **March 1st**

Do you need help applying Deep Learning to your research?

ai4life@eurobioimaging.eu <https://bit.ly/AI4Life-2nd-open-call> ai4life@eurobioimaging.eu

Funded by the European Union

OPEN CALL for Bioimage Analysis Support

- Automated species annotation in turbid waters
- Optimizing calcium image acquisition with ML denoising algorithms
- Diatom symbioses at planetary scale
- Automated segmentation of actin filaments in intact cells
- Enhancing the effective resolution of intravital microscopy with digital ExM
- Ultrastructural protein mapping through CLEM
- NeuroScan - A 3D human motor neuron disease platform for HTS

ai4life@eurobioimaging.eu <https://bit.ly/AI4Life-2nd-open-call> ai4life@eurobioimaging.eu

Funded by the European Union

OPEN CALL Bioimage Analysis Support

Apply by **Dec 16, 2024**

Do you need help applying Deep Learning to your research?

ai4life@eurobioimaging.eu <https://bit.ly/AI4Life-3rd-open-call> ai4life@eurobioimaging.eu

Funded by the European Union

OPEN CALL Bioimage Analysis Support

- Improving nuclei segmentation using CellProfiler and StarDist
- Feeding or Fading? Automated image analysis of white corals' behaviour to unlock natural patterns, stress responses, and conservation needs responses, and conservation needs
- 3D Matrix Motility Map (3DM²)
- The speed of life in trees - linking wood anatomy with wood lifespan and tree growth
- Imprints of Wind Disturbances on Wood Anatomy
- Detection of Nuclear Pore Complexes with shape variability imaged by DNA PAINT
- Segmentation of sparse bacteria in human tissue
- Automatic microtubule doublet picking in tomograms

ai4life@eurobioimaging.eu <https://bit.ly/AI4Life-3rd-open-call> ai4life@eurobioimaging.eu

Funded by the European Union

2.6.1.3. Challenges

Open Challenges allow computational experts to improve on the best existing methodological approaches to solve a given image analysis task. These challenges led to a healthy competition within the computational community.

Originally, the project aimed to derive Challenge problems directly from the AI4Life Open Calls. However, early experience revealed limitations with this approach, particularly regarding dataset readiness, since many submissions lacked sufficient data volume or quality to support a robust benchmarking challenge.

As a result, we revised our strategy: rather than building Challenges around individual Open Call projects, we began designing them based on broadly relevant and high-impact problems that were recurrently identified across multiple Open Call submissions. This realisation led us to focus on image restoration and denoising, which makes it possible to build a high-quality, generisable dataset and reference benchmarks. Throughout the project, AI4Life organised three separate challenges ([Denoising Challenge](#), [Denoising Challenge 2025](#), [Calcium Imaging Denoising Challenge](#)) and ran them using the [Grand Challenge](#) platform. Winning solutions will be published for each Challenge.

2.6.1.4. Events

AI4Life organised regular **training events** that were open to all interested participants. These focused on practical applications of AI methods for bioimage analysis. Recordings and training materials were made available whenever possible, further extending their impact.

Project partners actively represented the project at **national, European, and international conferences**, often using the branding materials that AI4Life created and distributed to increase visibility.

Members of AI4Life also contributed to conference organisation in leading roles. They ensured that AI4Life activities and outcomes were highlighted in the program whenever possible. Key examples are the NEUBIAS Training Academy and Symposium in 2023 in Porto and the I2K (*From Images to Knowledge*) conference in Milan in 2024.

Last but not least, AI4Life supported developer-facing hackathons (CoFests) with a dual purpose:

1. Engaging creators of popular image analysis software, including industry partners, to encourage the adoption of AI4Life standards, libraries, and models (via [Biolm.io](https://biolm.io)).
2. Collaborating with the developer community to co-design and implement solutions for technical challenges.

Together, these activities maximised the dissemination and exploitation of AI4Life results and built strong connections with diverse communities.

2.6.1.5. Engagement with industry and other projects/initiatives

AI4Life overlaps with a variety of projects at different levels and industry. A map describing the status of their interactions has been created and distributed to the partners.

AI4Life established a fruitful industry collaboration with Leica Microsystems, focused on integrating AI4Life resources with Leica's AIVIA platform. With this, we explored how community-driven AI models shared through the Biolmage Model Zoo can be deployed in commercial imaging environments, reaching a broader user base.

In parallel, AI4Life has joined forces with the AI4EOSC project, which develops the AI4OS platform for deploying AI models on EOSC resources. AI4EOSC created a dedicated flavour of AI4OS for AI4Life, enabling users to launch models within the platform.

These collaborations strengthen connections with academic and commercial partners, ensuring project outcomes are adopted.

2.6.1.6. Data and model sharing

AI4Life is strongly committed to open science and FAIR principles. All the data derived from the project activities are openly shared through the [Biolmage Archive](#), where a dedicated gallery highlights AI-ready datasets, curated and annotated for reuse. Additional datasets have also been made accessible via Zenodo.

Trained AI models are shared openly through the [Biolmage Model Zoo](#), where they are available for direct download with attached metadata and integration with widely used image analysis tools from the AI4Life Community partners.

AI4Life has also developed the [Model Evaluation Platform](#) to connect datasets and models more directly, which builds bridges between the Biolmage Archive and the Biolmage Model Zoo. This platform enables benchmarking of models on archived datasets.

2.6.1.7. Standards and standardisation efforts

A significant milestone was the organisation of a workshop by the BioImage Archive in January 2023 with 45 international experts, resulting in the MIFA recommendations (Metadata, Incentives, Formats, Accessibility) for sharing annotated AI-ready datasets. These guidelines, now published in Nature Methods¹, propose metadata standards for annotations, incentives to recognise dataset creation, adoption of interoperable formats (e.g., OME-Zarr), and deposition of datasets in FAIR-compliant repositories such as the BioImage Archive.

For AI model sharing, AI4Life has advanced bioimage.io specifications and supporting libraries. The bioimageio.spec package provides a versioned metadata format for pre-trained models, while bioimageio.core offers framework-specific adapters and utilities. Together, they ensure that community and third-party tools can execute models consistently and interoperably. Model packages include metadata for provenance, citation, and links to datasets and training code, making them entirely FAIR and easily reusable.

2.6.1.8. AI4Life Help Desk

The AI4Life Help Desk was established to provide a single point of contact for researchers, imaging facility staff, and developers interested in applying AI to bioimaging. It guided publishing datasets and annotations, sharing and documenting models with the AI4Life metadata standard, and accessing project resources.

¹ <https://www.nature.com/articles/s41592-025-02835-8>

2.6.2. AI4Life Key Exploitable Results

Building on the overall identification and characterisation of project results and outputs, the AI4Life Steering Committee further evaluated the exploitation potential of the identified results, leading to the selection of nine Key Exploitable Results (KERs) with high exploitation potential and benefit, mainly, but not only, for the scientific community:

KER 1	BioImage.io website (BioImage Model Zoo)
Short description	BioImage.IO drives high technological impact by democratizing access to AI models for bioimage analysis, fostering collaboration, and accelerating scientific discoveries.
Result type	INFRA: Infrastructure (improved)
Type of potential	High scientific potential; High technological, business, or economic potential
Target group	Researchers, End users (practitioners, farmers, etc.), Research Infrastructures
Steps undertaken towards exploitation	Prototyping in a production environment; Pilot, demonstration, or testing

KER 2	Specification BioImage.IO model description
Short description	Standardises metadata of pre-trained models to allow programmatic access.
Result type	METH: Method, material, technology, design (improved)
Type of potential	High scientific potential; High technological, business, or economic potential
Target group	Researchers, Research Infrastructures
Steps undertaken towards exploitation	Publication and open development; Contribution to standards

KER 3	BioEngine for model test run
Short description	BioEngine creates a high technological impact by streamlining data management, promoting efficient collaboration, and scaling to meet increasing data and computing demands.
Result type	SERV: Service (improved)
Type of potential	High technological, business, or economic potential; High scientific potential
Target group	Researchers, Research institutes, EU institutions and/or agencies, Research infrastructures
Steps undertaken towards exploitation	Prototyping in a production environment; Pilot, demonstration, or testing; Business plan

KER 4	Improved Hypha with AI Agent support
Short description	Hypha now supports building AI agent systems, connecting distributed tools beyond life sciences for automated data management, chat assistants, and scientific discovery.
Result type	PROD: Product (improved)
Type of potential	High technologic, business or economic potential; High scientific potential
Target group	Researchers, Innovators, EU institutions and/or agencies, Policy-makers and authorities, international, Policy-makers and authorities, national, Policy-makers and authorities, regional or local, Citizens, Standardisation bodies, End users (practitioners, farmers, etc.), Education/training organisation/learners, Research Infrastructures, Business accelerator providers
Steps undertaken towards exploitation	Prototyping in production environment; Pilot, demonstration or testing; Business plan

KER 5	BioImage.IO Chatbot
Short description	Allows life and computational scientists to find, test, use, and provide pre-trained image analysis models, easing AI adoption, sharing insights, and promoting reproducible research.
Result type	SERV: Service (new)
Type of potential	High scientific potential; High technological, business, or economic potential
Target group	Researchers, End users (practitioners, farmers, etc.), Research Infrastructures
Steps undertaken towards exploitation	Prototyping in a production environment

KER 6	Data services
Short description	Data services include a) community standards for AI-ready data (images + annotations with sufficient metadata to enable reuse), b) curated AI-ready datasets with ground truth annotations for model training benchmarking and annotation, c) large heterogeneous image datasets without specific annotations, for unsupervised model training or foundation model preconditioning, and d) a deposition service allowing members of the community publishing AI models to deposit their images and ground truth data to enable model reproducibility.
Result type	SERV: Service (new and improved)
Type of potential	High scientific potential
Target group	Researchers, Innovators, Standardisation bodies, End users (practitioners, farmers, etc.), Education/training organisation/learners, Research Infrastructures
Steps undertaken towards exploitation	Quality improved through curation; Continued development; Prototyping in a production environment; Pilot, demonstration or testing; Contribution to standards; Feasibility study

KER 7	AI4Life Open Calls Documentation and Reproducibility Materials
Short description	AI4Life Open Calls offered life scientists free expert consultation and joint solutions for common bioimage analysis problems, producing open workflows, data, and models for the wider community.
Result type	SERV: Service (new)
Type of potential	High scientific potential
Target group	Researchers, End users (practitioners, farmers, etc.), Research Infrastructures
Steps undertaken towards exploitation	Pilot, demonstration or testing; Enabling others to do the same/similar analyses; Potential reuse as teaching materials/ exercises

KER 8	AI4Life Public Challenges
Short description	Tasks, task descriptions, collected data, and associated metrics are a reusable product to be exploited by all methods researchers who want to measure their new methods against other existing methods. This facilitates methods research.
Result type	PROD: Product (new)
Type of potential	High scientific potential
Target group	Researchers, End users (practitioners, farmers, etc.), Research Infrastructures
Steps undertaken towards exploitation	Pilot, demonstration or testing; Ranking of existing methods for everyone to look up; Enabling others to benchmark against reported solutions

KER 9	Community building (user and developer engagement)
Short description	Promotes broad community-driven use & development of AI-based image analysis solutions in the life sciences built around the AI4Life resources & services, enabling sustainability of all project resources, services, and KERs.

Result type	STAFF: Qualified personnel
Type of potential	High scientific potential; High technological, business, or economic potential
Target group	Researchers, Research Infrastructures, End users (practitioners, farmers, etc), Innovators, Education/training organisation/learners, Computational developers
Steps undertaken towards exploitation	Establishment of an AI4Life community governance and participation framework; Organization of community engagement events, activities and pathways to foster continuous engagement

Beyond the general exploitation steps indicated in the tables, pathways for the exploitation of the KERs that the AI4Life partners pursue include integration into existing research infrastructures (Euro-BioImaging), reuse and further development through affiliated projects (e.g., AI4EOSC, RI-SCALE), and adoption by tool developers and service providers. The project also promotes uptake by ensuring alignment with EOSC and broader European Open Science priorities.

2.6.2.1. Horizon Results Booster service

To further develop and review the identified KERs and their exploitation strategies, the consortium was selected to participate in the [Horizon Results Booster \(HRB\) Service](#). To comply with the service's format and gain the most benefit from it, the following KER

“packages” were selected for joint review and elaboration together with an external expert:

- HRB KER1: BMZ, BioEngine & Chatbot
- HRB KER2: Data services
- HRB KER3: User and developer engagement

The expert guided the refining and strengthening of the project’s KER exploitation strategies. As a result, the consortium was able to review and enhance its KERs, revise and complement existing exploitation plans, and outline clearer paths for future use of project results. The process and results are described in a detailed report shared with the project partners.

3. Sustainability

AI4Life has taken a proactive approach to ensure its results remain available, impactful, and maintained beyond the project's lifetime. The sustainability strategy builds on three complementary pillars: community co-development, infrastructure partnerships, and strategy continuity through funding and collaboration.

3.1. Community engagement as a sustainability pillar

A central aspect of AI4Life's sustainability is its emphasis on community co-development. The project has onboarded new Community Partners, launched digital badges for recognition, and offered joint dissemination opportunities.

The diagram below illustrates AI4Life's approach to community engagement as a continuous cycle: it begins with gathering feedback (Step 1) and identifying community needs (Step 2), which informs priority setting (Step 3) and the co-development of tools, datasets, and standards (Step 4). This, in turn, drives wider adoption and validation (Step 5), enhances scientific impact (Step 6), and ultimately nurtures long-term sustainability (Step 7) through shared ownership and responsibility.

3.1.1. Community Partners

Community Partners comprise this strategy's core component, contributing compatible models, datasets, tools, and expertise. By embedding sustainability within a distributed network of contributors, AI4Life created a co-maintenance model in which resources are supported and advanced by a broad base of stakeholders, extending beyond the original consortium and ensuring that the project's resources and services are meaningful and relevant for the scientific community.

3.1.2 Industry engagement

AI4Life has actively contacted the industry to access and contribute AI models to the BMZ, data in the Biolmage Archive, and participate in Open Calls, workshops, and challenges. The project met with industry stakeholders, including the Euro-Biolmaging Industry Board, Bayer, Roche, Zeiss, and Leica. Company representatives have participated in the AI4Life hackathons to exchange and collaborate with the project members. A prime outcome of these collaborations is the integration of several BMZ models into Leica's AIVIA microscopy image analysis software, making them available to a broader user community. Additionally, the AI4Life partner KTH established Amun AI, a spin-off company which will develop and exploit some of the components derived from the project's infrastructure. The company is developing Hypha Cloud, a plug-and-play version of the Hypha platform to enable secure and scalable cloud computing for sensitive data.

3.2. Integration into the European landscape

3.2.1. European Research Infrastructures

Sustainability has been further anchored by embedding AI4Life outcomes within the European research infrastructure landscape. Euro-Biolmaging ERIC, as the coordinating infrastructure, together with partner infrastructures such as EMBRC, Instruct ERIC, EU-Openscreen, and EMPHASIS, provides a long-term institutional home for key outputs, ensuring continuity of access, integration, and support. AI4Life's data services have been thoroughly integrated into EMBL-EBI's and the Biolmage Archive's overall data strategy, ensuring maintenance and further development. Additionally, the AI4Life partners Euro-Biolmaging ERIC, Instruct ERIC, and EMBL, together with ELIXIR, are forming the EOSC Life Science Research candidate Node that may act as a platform to further embed AI4Life services into the EOSC in the future. To this end, AI4Life has also joined forces with the AI4EOSC project, resulting in the integration of Biolmage Model

Zoo AI models into AI4EOSC's AI4OS platform, thus already now making them available to researchers directly through the EOSC.

3.2.2. Collaboration with other projects and organisations

AI4Life partners have actively pursued collaborations with related European and global initiatives and projects, including the alignment with initiatives like the RDA, EGI, RI-SCALE, AI4EOSC, GloBIAS, and the Galaxy community. Such collaborations extend the reach of AI4Life results and connect them to broader European and global efforts.

3.3. Beyond the project: A new governance framework

AI4Life partners are exploring follow-up funding opportunities under Horizon Europe and other national and international programs to maintain momentum beyond the project's lifetime. To ensure its continuity, the BMZ now operates under an AI4Life community governance framework coordinated by Euro-BioImaging and supported by the founding partners KTH/SciLifeLab, EMBL, EMBL-EBI, Human Technopole, UC3M, and ITQB-NOVA, all of them committing to maintenance and further development of the BMZ-related resources.

The governance structure consists of:

- Management Board: sets strategy and roadmap.
- Technical Board: drives infrastructure and software development.
- Community Board: gathers feedback, coordinates contributions, and represents the broader community.

AI4Life Community Governance

This participatory governance model helps ensure that AI4Life resources are continuously updated, reused, and improved by the wider bioimaging community. Weekly open meetings, transparent agendas, and shared documentation on GitHub keep the process accessible and accountable.

4. Conclusion

The AI4Life Dissemination and Exploitation plan demonstrates a comprehensive strategy to communicate, share, and sustain the project's outputs. By combining stakeholder-targeted outreach, standardised branding, multi-channel dissemination, and structured exploitation of results, AI4Life has maximised the visibility and uptake of its AI-based image analysis resources.

Through Open Calls, Challenges, and community-driven initiatives, the project provided life scientists with actionable AI tools and engaged computational experts in advancing bioimage analysis methods. Identifying nine Key Exploitable Results (KERs) highlights the strategic potential of AI4Life outputs for scientific, technological, and societal impact.

Sustainability beyond the funded period is anchored in three complementary pillars: co-development with a broad community, embedding outputs within European research infrastructures, and ensuring continuity via a participatory governance framework. By establishing these mechanisms, AI4Life guarantees that its services, datasets, models, and standards will remain actively maintained, widely used, and continuously improved by the broader bioimaging community.

Ultimately, AI4Life provides a model for integrating AI solutions into life sciences research, promoting collaboration, reproducibility, and long-term innovation across European and international communities.